

EFFECT OF WORKPLACE INCIVILITY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Imen Javed Khan

Department of Human Resource Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, International Islamic University
Islamabad

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20844690>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 24 April 2026

Accepted: 06 June 2026

Published: 21 June 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Imen Javed Khan

Abstract

This study has been conducted for the purpose of exploring the fact that whether emotional intelligence is linked with workplace incivility or not. Moreover, it was also searched that which component of EI was closely related to WI. Additionally, this study will also explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and the two sub factors of Big Five Traits Theory agreeableness and extraversion. A questionnaire was designed to serve the purpose of collecting data including four sub-sections covering each variable. 300 questionnaires were circulated for this purpose in various public and private sector organizations, banks, educational institutions, regulatory authorities, etc. 202 surveys were returned and 194 were sort out for data analysis after screening. To investigate the research hypothesis, three tests were conducted comprising of reliability tests, correlations and hierarchical multiple regressions. The results of these tests showed a positive relation between workplace incivility and emotional intelligence. Moreover, a positive relation was also found between emotional intelligence and extraversion. A perfect positive correlation came out to be in between emotional intelligence and agreeableness. Future studies should test if EI recovery from incivility differs across cultures, to build cross-cultural COR theory. Research must explore new digital incivility forms like AI monitoring rudeness or Zoom fatigue, as flexible work evolves beyond email/Slack. Longitudinal experiments are needed to validate which HRM interventions actually reverse EI damage, moving beyond the study's observational design to casual evidence and whether this damage is temporary or permanent.

CHAPTER 1
INTRODUCTION

"Emotions may be felt both too much and too little, and in both cases not well; but to feel them at the right times with reference to the right objects towards the right people with the right motive, and in the right way is what is both intermediate and best, and this is characteristics of virtue."(Nicomachean Ethics)

This quote was stated by Aristotle some 2,300 years ago which demonstrates emotions as a virtue and it can be recognized as the most ancient

definition of emotional intelligence as a human characteristic but for the last two and half decade emotional intelligence has attained its significance in scientific investigation. (Moshe Zeidner, Gerald Matthews, Richard D. Roberts, 2009). Emotional intelligence is an essential factor responsible for determining success in life and psychological wellbeing, seems to play an important role in shaping the interaction between individuals and their work environment.

The major components of EI I-e perceiving, understanding and regulating emotions helps in

facilitating the proficiency of employees to have command of workplace events and reactions to those events (Schutte S.Nicola, Natasha M. Loi, 2014) therefore, higher level of emotional intelligence might be linked to lower levels of adverse reactions to the events which may lead to workplace incivility. Therefore, we believe that workplace incivility has higher chances of being in relation with emotional intelligence.

The purpose of the study is to explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and workplace incivility.

Emotional intelligence is being pursued as a hot topic not only in any psychological research but also social sciences, workforce interactions, job outcomes, education and medical nursing field. It plays an important role in our daily interactions and professional lives and also has a great influence on our personality traits and behavior outcomes. Many researchers have pinpointed the significance of emotional intelligence of the employees as a substantial antecedent of work outcomes, work attitudes and other behaviors. (Goleman;1998, Carmeli,Jozman;2006, Wrong & Law, 2002)

Practically, EI makes an individual more psychologically aware of his own and other's emotions. This consciousness makes one's character and disposition to be more civilized in behaviors at workplace which in turn make him easier going in social interactions and will give him the status of being more acceptable by the organizational environment. This characteristic will then lead to further positive outcomes which will in result lower the levels of inefficient and counterproductive behaviors (Zainab , Karim, 2013).

Schutte and Hine (2011) have suggested in their research findings that intervening at the level of emotional intelligence can be a good option to overcome the problems of workplace incivility.

Although Zainab and Karim (2013) have tried to develop a relation between workplace incivility, counterproductive work behavior and EI but emotional intelligence was only used as a moderating factor between the two variables.

Therefore, this research can become a way opener for new researches to this untapped dimension of

organizational behavior to access and analyze the effects of emotional intelligence on inappropriate behavior in workplace. Furthermore, organizations may also focus on the regulation and monitoring of emotions of their staff members to curb the issues caused by occupational immoral behavior, thus strengthening the structural and social environment of their firm. Moreover, the research will contribute in proving the reliability and validity of instruments developed by Schutte (1998) for emotional intelligence, Shim (2010) for workplace Incivility and Big Five Inventory.

In the light of these objectives and on the basis of previous research findings, we would like to answer the following research questions.

- Whether there is any relation between Emotional Intelligence and Workplace Incivility?
- Which dimensions of EI affect the most on Workplace Incivility?
- What are the factors relating to EI that may cause incivility at workplace?

Research Purpose and Research Questions

Problem Statement:

The major research question addressed in this study is as follows:

Is there any (direct/indirect) relation between emotional intelligence and Workplace Incivility? If yes, then how workplace incivility effects emotional intelligence?

H1: Workplace incivility has an impact on the employee's emotional intelligence

H2: Workplace incivility affects the employee's agreeableness.

H3: Workplace incivility affects the employee's extraversion capacity.

H4: Emotional intelligence is positively related to extraversion of the personnel.

H5: Emotional intelligence has a positive relation with agreeableness.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

❖ Emotional Intelligence:

Another definition of emotional intelligence was given by Goleman, the author of Emotional Intelligence in 1990. He defined it as "An array of

non-cognitive capabilities, competencies, and skills that influence one's ability to succeed in coping with environmental demands and pressures" (Goleman.D, 1995).

Definition:

The term emotional intelligence was first properly defined by Salovey and Mayer (1990) in their academic papers. According to them, "*emotional intelligence is a subset of social intelligence that involves ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions*" (Mayer, J. D., DiPaolo, M., & Salovey, P, 1990)

At first, the concept of Emotional Intelligence was primarily emerged by the evolution of cognitive intelligence, which was linked to an individual's memory and problem solving ability, into non cognitive intelligence forms. (Thorndike, Stein, 1937). At that time Emotional intelligence was more regarded as social intelligence but it was not before 1990 that Mayer's and Salovey had scientifically described the term "Emotional Intelligence". However, the term EI gained its popularity with the publication of Goleman's book "Emotional Intelligence- Is EI better than IQ?" (Goleman.D, 1995) Which captured the attention of various researchers, academics and practitioners. Certain emotions such as anger, happiness, fear and an individual's state of body, mind, mood and preferences have a significant effect on the way individuals think, their decision making and performance of different activities. (Salovey, Peter et al, 1989). These emotions may have a significant influence on how a person will react and interact with his/her working environment.

The higher levels of emotional intelligence in workers are linked with a number of general positive intrapersonal outcomes (Schutte,N.S, Malouff,J.M, 2013) which bring a positive effect on the personal well-being of the individuals resulting in greater life satisfaction. (Bracket,M.A, Mayer, J.D, 2003). Greater levels of EI are also related with a cooperative behavior, (Schutte, 2011), relationship satisfaction (Malouff,J,Schutte,N , 2014) and better

interpersonal relationships (Lopes,P.N., 2004) Higher scores in emotional intelligence are also found to be in relation with greater satisfaction with workplace social support which in turn was connected to workplace flourishing. (Schutte , Natasha, 2014)

Models of Emotional Intelligence

Since the emergence of EI concept to date, four major models were developed by scholars to explain the dimensions of emotional intelligence. All these models can be measured by many ways for instance the model developed by Mayer and Salovey can be measured by MCEIT as well as the measure developed by Schutte. (Schutte S.Nicola et al, 1998)

1) Mental ability based model:

Mayer and Salovey in 2004 proposed the ability based model of emotional intelligence that divided the skills and abilities of EI into four major dimensions which are as follows (Mayer, Salovey, Caruso, 2004)

- Perceiving emotions.
- Using emotions to facilitate thoughts
- Understanding emotions
- Managing emotions

Mayer Salovey and Caruso developed an MSEIT ability test to measure these dimensions by evaluating actual performance. On the basis of this mode, Schutte has developed 33 items scale to measure emotional intelligence through the ability of an individual to perceive, use, understand and regulate emotions. (Schutte S.Nicola et al, 1998)

2) Boyatzis-Goleman model

Boyatzis- Goleman model was a second major model that was formalized in 2004 by Boystzis-Goleman. It was formulated on the basis of Mayer and Salovey's theory of social and emotional competencies that linked with superior performance with emotional intelligence. The model revolves around four basic clusters. Framework of emotional competencies is divided into personal competencies and social competencies relating to recognition and regulation. (Goleman D. , 2004)

- **Self-awareness:** including emotional self-awareness, accurate self-assessment, self-confidence
- **Self-management:** measures self-control, trustworthiness, conscientiousness, adaptability, achievement drive and initiative.
- **Social awareness:** focusing empathy, service orientation and organizational awareness
- **Relationship management:** including developing other, influence, communication, conflict management, leadership, change catalyst, building bonds, teamwork and collaboration

3) Bar on model:

The Bar On model has measured emotional intelligence on the basis of EQI scales. EQ-I or the emotional quotient inventory was the basis of this model that is the self-report measure of emotional social intelligence. (Bar-On, 2006)

- **Intrapersonal;** including self-regard, emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, independence and self-actualization
- **Interpersonal;** covering empathy, social responsibility and interpersonal relationship
- **Stress management;** measures stress tolerance and impulse control
- **Adaptability;** focusing on reality testing, flexibility and problem solving.
- **General mood;** studying optimism and happiness.

4) Trait emotional intelligence:

This is, by far the latest and a comprehensive ability model formed on the basis of the model proposed by Mayer and Salovey in 1997. The model comprises of four components named as: (Petrides.K.V et al, 2007)

- **Well-being:** including self-confidence, happiness and optimism
- **Sociability:** explaining social competence, assertiveness and emotional management of others
- **Self-control:** focusing on stress management, emotion regulation and low impulsiveness

- **Emotionality:** measuring emotional perception of self and others, emotion expression and empathy

These dimensions are measured by the development of Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue). No matter what the number of models is and what dimensions each model has specified, every model of Emotional Intelligence was based on the initial work of Mayer and Salovey's description of emotional intelligence ability based theory which is considered as the most cohesive and comprehensive model of EI and a number of dimensions of other models can be integrated into ability based theory. (Schutte, Mallouff et al, 1998)

❖ Workplace Incivility

It's been one and a half decade since the term workplace incivility was first introduced in 1999 By Anderson Pearson. After that it has been studied in various antisocial behaviour disciplines including management, education, nursing etc. But very few practical researches are being conducted to analyse the implications of workplace incivility in practical sense.

Definition:

According to Pearson & Andersson, "*Workplace incivility is low-intensity deviant behavior with ambiguous intent to harm the target, in violation of workplace norms for mutual respect.*" (Christine M. Pearson, Lynne M. Andersson, 1999). This definition has been accepted and cited in a number of articles, journals and research papers (Martin, Hine, 2005) (Holm, Torkelson, 2015). Workplace Incivility has been distinguished from its sister concepts of aggression, violence, a deviant and antisocial behavior as it is considered least harmful of them all and resides on the lowest level on the scale of Mistreatment in organizations. (Christine M. Pearson, Lynne M. Andersson, 1999)

The roots of incivility are dug deep down into workplace deviance, (Taylor, S.G.,Pattie,M.W, 2014) therefore despite of the fact it is considered a low intensity deviant behaviour, it is still regarded equally perilous as workplace bullying

(Hershcovis, 2011) even eye rolling, ignoring other working mates, using cell phones during office meetups can be equated with yelling in terms of its effect on job satisfaction, turn over intentions of employees and other behavioural outcomes. Such attitudes like gossiping, aggression, excluding people and hostility (Schilpzand, Erez & Pater, 2014) can prove disastrous for individuals and teams as well as the organizations. (Nicholson, T. Griffin, B., 2014). Its harmful effects are clearly depicted in empirical researches where workplace incivility is found to be associated with greater levels of lower engagement (Trudel, J., Reio, T.G, 2011) and affective commitment (Hershcovis, 2011), higher emotional exhaustion (Sliter, M., Jex, S., Wolford, K., McInnerney, J, 2010), turnover (Lim, S., Lee, A., 2011) and withdrawal intentions (Itzkovich, 2015) and more counterproductive work behaviour. (Taylor, S.G, Kluemper, D.H, 2012).

According to the research conducted by Martin and Beckman, it was suggested that emotional intelligence of employees can play a role in controlling workplace deviant behaviours. (Martin, J.; Knopoff, K.; Beckman, C., 1998). Therefore, we suggest the following hypothesis.

H1: Workplace incivility has an impact on the employee's emotional intelligence

❖ The Five-factor Model of Personality

The five factor model, generally known as Big Five Personality Model is a hierarchical organization of personality traits derived on the basis of the early research of Allport, and Obdert (1936) on human behavior traits. This model explains personality in terms of five basic dimensions; Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Openness to experience and Neuroticism. (Robert R. McCrae, Oliver P. John, 1992)

The pattern of feelings, behaviours and thoughts of an individual is termed as Personality (Hamid Afshar et al, 2015). Human disposition is based on personality which is dependent on the individual's emotional state and his existing environmental and social conditions. (Ozer, D.J., Benet-Martinez, V., 2006)

➤ Agreeableness:

Agreeableness is a degree to which an individual is loving, patient, warm, trusting, and sensitive.

Individuals that score high on agreeableness are helpful considerate, friendly, forgiving, generous, and can easily get along with others. They also tend to be compassionate, cooperative and willing to compromise their desires for the sake of others. (Kuldeep Kumat, Arti Bakhshi, 2010)

Agreeableness is the extent to measure whether an individual possess a pro social orientation or he has an antagonist personality. An agreeable person will consider the betterment, welfare and interests of the people around him. (Mohsin Atta, Muhammad Ather, Dr. Maher Bano, 2013)

Agreeableness is regarded as a determinant of various intergroup stereotypes and attitudes. (Duckitt, J., Sibley, C.G., 2010). People getting low scores on the scale of agreeableness are likely to prefer such actions that will be beneficial for serving their own interest with a very much lesser concern of other's interest. Thus, viewing the world as a socially competitive ground and will therefore exhibit attitudes that ensure group dominance at the cost of others (Rhiannon N. Turner et al, 2014). Therefore, we can predict that

H2: Workplace incivility affects the employee's agreeableness.

➤ Extraversion:

Extraversion is an extent to which individual is inclined towards sociability, talkativeness, and excitement seeking. (Costa. P.T , McCrae. R.R, 1992). Such individuals have the tendency to be friendlier and can easily adapt to new working environment as compared to their introverts counterparts (Teng. C.I, Jeng SP, 2008). Extraversion relates to a more optimistic and energetic view to the world instead of a pessimistic vision. According to the study conducted by Wang (2014), the individuals scoring low on both extraversion and agreeableness are more likely to get indulged in interpersonal deviant behaviors. (Wang, Harms, Mackey, 2015). This leads us to our next hypothesis.

H3: Workplace incivility affects the employee's extraversion capacity.

The Big Five Factors are (chart recreated from John & Srivastava, 1999)

Table 1: Big Five Dimensions Facet (and correlated trait adjective)

Extraversion vs. introversion Gregariousness (sociable)	Assertiveness (forceful)
	Activity (energetic)
	Excitement-seeking (adventurous)
	Positive emotions (enthusiastic)
Agreeableness vs. antagonism Trust (forgiving)	Warmth (outgoing)
	Straightforwardness (not demanding)
	Altruism (warm)
	Compliance (not stubborn)
	Modesty (not show-off)
	Tender-mindedness (sympathetic)

Relation between EI and Five factor model of Personality

Emotional intelligence has been found to be highly correlated with extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and neuroticism but moderately related to openness to experience. (Brackett, M.A, Mayer, J.D., 2003). People who are high in emotional intelligence are more extrovert and conscientious than the people who are less emotionally intelligent. (Day, A.L., Therrien, D.L, Carroll, S.A., 2005)

It has been found that Emotional intelligence is positively correlated with extraversion, openness, conscientiousness and agreeableness (Hundani, M.N., Redzuan, M., Hamsan. H., 2012). Shulman and Hameen over (2006) has found that EI has a positive relation with extraversion and openness (Shulman, E. T., Hemenover, S.H., 2006). It has examined by Sala in 2002 that EI measured by Goleman’s Emotional Competence Inventory (1998) was significantly related to extraversion, openness to experience and conscientiousness. From this we can derive our hypothesis:

H4: Emotional intelligence is positively related to extraversion of the personnel.

(Sala, 2002). After the results of Mayer-Salovey-Curuso’s “Emotional Intelligence”, it has found that only two traits related to Emotional Intelligence which are Agreeableness and Openness to experience. (Brackett, M.A, Mayer, J.D., 2003).

It has found that EI has negatively correlated with neuroticism but positively correlated with extraversion (Matthews, G., Emo, A.K., Funke, et al, 2006). The measures of Emotional intelligence shows the positive correlation with agreeableness, openness to experience and conscientiousness while significant relation with extraversion. (Petrides, K.V., Furnham. A., 2001). Many researches have evidences which show that emotional intelligence was a strongest predictor of extraversion, agreeableness, openness and neuroticism.

(Athota, V.S., O’connor, P.J, Jackson, C., 2009). On the basis of this background, we can hypothesize that:

H5: Emotional intelligence has a positive relation with agreeableness.

Theoretical Framework

After an extensive peruse of current and historical literature and careful interpretation of the future implications proposed by well-known researchers, I came to an agreement to develop a comprehensive model that would present the crux of this basic research. The model includes a set of dependent, independent and co- dependent variables. Workplace incivility would act as an independent variable that is supposed to affect the emotional intelligence of an employee which is a dependent variable. Emotional intelligence will impact on the agreeableness and extraversion of the personnel. It is important to note that

although prima facie the model appears to be having a relationship between an independent workplace incivility and the dependent agreeableness and extraversion mediated by emotional intelligence. But in reality, the model is proposing a combination of two different models,

where first relation is between workplace incivility (independent) & emotional intelligence (dependent), and a second relation between emotional intelligence acting as an independent variable and extraversion & agreeableness acting as dependent variables.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

CHAPTER 3
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To search out for the answers of the aforementioned problem statement, I have chosen the quantitative research methods because the results of the study are meant to be generalized from the conclusions drawn from the sample. Therefore, the nature of this study demands the quantitative research method technique. (Holton III, E. F., & Burnett, M. F. (2005). *The basics of quantitative research*. In, 2005). As the research variables are taken as it is and we aim to search for the possible association between workplace incivility and emotional intelligence. Therefore, this study is considered as a non-experimental correlational research design study. (Gall, M, D., Gall, J. P., & Borg, W, R., 2007)

Data Collection Procedure

Population:

The working population chosen for the purpose of this research comprises of the participants working in diversified sectors such as banking, educational, information and technology ,government, regulatory bodies ,federal agencies, NGO’s , electronic media personnel etc. Due care was taken while selecting the population that the

responses generated were acquired from across genders, age limits, experience tenure, and through incumbents holding positions at various job levels.

Sample Size:

A sample size of a total number of 300 questionnaires was dispersed among the employees of the foresaid sectors. Out of these only 202 were retrieved. Eight of the questionnaires among these were rejected due to partial completion and on the discovery of fake responses. Thus, a sample of 194 questionnaires was used as a predictor of the aforementioned variables. The response rate was 65.3%.

Sample Demographics:

The questionnaires shall be dispersed across the public and private sectors or organizations residing in Islamabad and Rawalpindi (Pakistan). The minimum age level selected to respond would be 20 years or more while only the experienced and currently job holding candidates were targeted as they would be likely to respond about the uncivil practices observed at their workplace.

Measurement Instruments

- **Workplace Incivility:**

In order to measure the construct of workplace incivility, the UWBQ (Uncivil Workplace Behavior Questionnaire) instrument was used which was formulated by Martin & Hine IN 2005 (Martin, Hine, 2005). The instrument included a set of 20 questions (given in appendix) which focused on four dimensions of workplace incivility namely gossiping, exclusionary behavior, privacy invasion and hostility. The exclusionary behavior dimension includes questions such as “Avoided consulting you when they would normally expect to do so”. Each statement was followed by a 5 point Likert scale to record the response of correspondents ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This test holds an excellent concurrent and convergent validity by exhibiting a Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient figure of 0.92 whereas the value of Cronbach’s Alpha derived from this study came out to be 0.919.

- **Emotional Intelligence:**

A 33-item scale was used to measure the emotional intelligence quotient of respondents which was developed by Schutte in 1998 (Schutte, Mallouff et al, 1998) on the basis of the dimensions of emotional intelligence presented in the Mayer and Salovey’s model in 1990. (Mayer, J. D., DiPaolo, M., & Salovey, P, 1990). The set inculcates all the dimensions of emotional intelligence where first 13 items were used to measure appraisal and expression of emotional intelligence, 10 items were generated under the regulation category of emotions and the rest 10 were built on the basis of utilization of emotions category of the model. Moreover, each dimension includes the subcomponents of every category e.g. the dimension of regulation of emotion assesses the regulation of emotions in self as well as regulation of emotions in others. The internal consistency of this scale originally had the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of 0.90 (Schutte, Mallouff et al, 1998) while the internal consistency of this study came out to be 0.833.

- **Big Five Personality Traits:**

As the time needed to complete the instrument was an important consideration, therefore the 44-

item Big Five Inventory (BFI) instrument was chosen to assess the personality traits constructed by John, Donahu, and Kentle (1991). It is also considered as an efficient and flexible tool with short-phrase item format as compared to Goldberg’s (1992) 100-item TDA scale and the 240 item NEO questionnaire by McCrae and Costa (1992) (Oliver P.John, Sanjay Srivastava, 1999). The mean reliability of BFI is 0.83 while the individual trait reliabilities of extraversion and agreeableness in BFI came out to be 0.88 and 0.79 respectively. However, a potential limitation was predicted in the original measurement that the predictive validities were not determined by the constructors. (Oliver P.John, Sanjay Srivastava, 1999). Therefore, the validities of both variables came out to be as 0.44 and 0.624 for extraversion and agreeableness respectively.

Data Analysis

In order to test the proposed hypothesis, I ran multiple analysis techniques using SPSS software which calculated the descriptive statistics, Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient scores, and correlation coefficient. Descriptive statistics included the classification of certain control variables such as gender, education, experience etc. and their frequencies. The value of Cronbach’s Alpha are used to represent the internal consistency of the items whereas correlation coefficient describe the general nature of relationships among the proposed variables .In addition, hierarchal multiple regression analysis was conducted which is suitable when two or more independent variables are hypothesized to have a relationship with a single metric dependent variable. (Howell, 2007)

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

In this chapter, I will present the results of the survey conducted and the analysis of data. At first the descriptive statistics including frequency of control variables, reliability and correlation among the key variables are shown. After that the proposed model has been tested by utilizing the hierarchical multiple regressions with their

reported results. For all the statistical analysis procedures, the software SPSS 15 was used.

The collected data were analyzed to test the following hypotheses.

H1: Workplace incivility has an impact on the employee's emotional intelligence

H2: Workplace incivility affects the employee's agreeableness.

H3: Workplace incivility affects the employee's extraversion capacity.

H4: Emotional intelligence is positively related to extraversion of the personnel.

H5: Emotional intelligence has a positive relation with agreeableness.

Descriptive Statistics, Reliability and Correlations

Control Variables:

In this quantitative study, there was a need to control certain variables that were gender, education, experience and job title because there implicit impact over the other variables could result in a considerable anomaly in results. As the

variance in these factors of individuals can significantly affect their personality traits; most specifically emotional intelligence, workplace incivility, extraversion and agreeableness which are the epicenter of our discussion, therefore, before initiating the testing of our model, these variables were intentionally controlled.

Descriptive Statistics

The sample co-incidentally included equal size of male and female participants'. Nearly 63% of the candidates held Master's degree and 29% were having a Bachelor's degree. Nearly 5 % held MPhil and PhD degree, 2% were intermediate and only 1 % were of matriculation level

Education

Nearly 54% of the incumbents were having less than 5 years of experience while almost 25% had a minimal 6 to 10 years' experience; rest of the candidates had varied degree of 11 to 35 years of experience.

Table 2: Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Matric	2	1.0	1.0	1.0
Intermediate	4	2.1	2.1	3.1
Bachelors	56	28.9	28.9	32.0
Masters	123	63.4	63.4	95.4
M.Phil/PHD	9	4.6	4.6	100.0
Total	194	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Education

Experience

Based upon their educational background and experience tenure covered, nearly 56% of the candidates held positions in the middle level

hierarchy of their organization while 36% were having job titles in the lower level positions. More than 8% of the candidates belong to the top level class of the organization.

Table 3: Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 0-5 years	104	53.6	53.6	53.6
6-10 years	49	25.3	25.3	78.9
11-15 years	15	7.7	7.7	86.6
16-20 years	11	5.7	5.7	92.3
21-25 years	8	4.1	4.1	96.4
26-30 years	3	1.5	1.5	97.9
31-35 years	4	2.1	2.1	100.0
Total	194	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Experience

Job Title

More than half of the candidates (55.7%) belonged to the middle level cadre of their respective organizations while 36% represented

the lower level job titles. About 8% of the participants were the holders of upper level managerial positions.

Table 4: Job Title

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Lower Level	70	36.1	36.1	36.1
Middle Level	108	55.7	55.7	91.8
Top level	16	8.2	8.2	100.0
Total	194	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4: Job Title

Reliability Analysis:

The value of Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient between 0.6 and 1.0 can be regarded as acceptable scale of reliability analysis whereas then reliability score ranging between 0.8 to < 0.9 is stated as very good while the score of 0.9 is considered as excellent (Hair, J.F.J., Babin, B., Money, A.H., & Samuel, P., 2003).

The original Cronbach’s Alpha for the 33 items scale of emotional intelligence showed the internal consistency of 0.9 (Schutte S.Nicola et al, 1998) while our analysis has shown the reliability statistics of EI variable as 0.833 which is deemed to be good.

The internal consistency of workplace incivility was found to be excellent with the reliability score of 0.991 that is almost equivalent to the reliability score of the original test design that was 0.93. (JiHyun, 2010).

The reliability of the 8 items of personality trait extraversion was 0.44 which was not surprisingly as this result is consistent with the previous researches that indicated a low score of big five personality traits on the reliability scale (Mohsin Atta, Muhammad Ather, Dr. Maher Bano, 2013)..

The Cronbach’s alpha for 9 items of agreeableness was found out to be 0.624 which is consistent with the findings of previous researches using BFI (Samuel D. Gosling,* Peter J. Rentfrow, and William B. Swann Jr., 2003)

Correlation

The table 5 presents the respective correlations and internal consistency reliabilities of emotional intelligence, workplace incivility, extraversion, and agreeableness. The values mentioned within brackets represent Cronbach’s Alpha of all the variables.

Table 5: Correlation Statistics

	Gender	Job Title	Experience	Education	Emotional Intelligence	Agreeableness	Workplace Incivility	Extraversion
Gender	1	.000	-.070	.040	-.186(**)	-.186(**)	-.212(**)	-.042
Job Title		1	.370(**)	.386(**)	-.008	-.008	.143(*)	.023
Experience	-.070	.370(**)	1					
Education	.040	.386(**)	.152(*)	1				
Emotional Intelligence	-.186(**)	-.008	-.054	-.076	1 (.833)			
Agreeableness	-.186(**)	-.008	-.054	-.076	1.000(**)	1(.624)		
Workplace Incivility	-.212(**)	.143(*)	-.123	-.042	.210(**)	.210(**)	1 (.919)	
Extraversion	-.042	.023	.018		.242(**)		-.026	1(.444)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The coefficient of correlation exhibited contrasting relationships among the variables. The relationship between agreeableness and emotional intelligence came out to be + 1 .that showed a perfect correlation that was highly significant (p < 0.01) .A weak correlation was cited between the constructs of workplace incivility and emotional intelligence that were also highly significant (p <

0.01). An exactly similar relation was found between WI and agreeableness. The extraversion variable was again found to be weakly correlated with emotional intelligence at a high significance rate while it was no relation was found between extraversion and workplace incivility.

Table 6: Correlation of Workplace Incivility with the Components of Emotional Intelligence

		Workplace Incivility	EI regulation	EI expression	EI utilization
Workplace Incivility	Pearson Correlation	1	.215(**)	.129	.165(*)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003	.073	.022
	N	194	194	194	194

The table 6 shows the correlation between the sub dimensions of emotional intelligence and workplace incivility. The dimension of emotional regulation was found to be weakly correlated with workplace incivility with high level of significance (p<0.01). While the dimension of utilization of

emotions was weakly but significantly correlated with WI (p<0.05).

Hierarchical Multiple Regression Analysis:
i. Workplace incivility (Independent variable) and EI (Dependent variable)

In the model 1, we tested the hypothesis that workplace incivility is related to emotional intelligence. The result showed a significant

relation between workplace incivility and emotional intelligence and thus the hypothesis was supported. The result implies that greater the experience of a respondent with respect to workplace incivility, the more will be his emotional intelligence.

Table 7: WI & EI Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.210 ^a	.044	.039	.45362

a. Predictors: (Constant), WorkplaceIncivility

- A. Predictor: (Constant), Workplace incivility
- B. Dependent Variable: Emotional Intelligence

Table 8: WI & EI Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.918	.115		16.653	.000
	WorkplaceIncivility	.146	.049	.210	2.979	.003

a. Dependent Variable: EmotionalIntelligence

ii. Workplace incivility and EI regulation:

The regulation component of EI has been found to be the most crucial component that is significantly linked to workplace incivility. The regulation component of emotional intelligence is the most significantly related item in relation to workplace incivility. This is the clear indication that the relationship between workplace incivility and emotional intelligence is mainly relying on this construct.

Table 9: WI & EI regulation Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.215 ^a	.046	.041	.38997

a. Predictors: (Constant), WorkplaceIncivility

Table 10: WI & EI Regulation Coefficients

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.734	.099		17.512	.000
	WorkplaceIncivility	.128	.042	.215	3.053	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Elregulation

iii. Workplace Incivility (independent) and Agreeableness (dependent)

Just as the results of correlation, agreeableness is again exhibiting similar values as that of emotional intelligence even in significance here. The 44% figure shows a valid relationship b/w workplace incivility and agreeableness.

Table 11: WI & Agreeableness Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.210 ^a	.044	.039	.45362

a. Predictors: (Constant), WorkplaceIncivility

Table 12: WI & Agreeableness Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.918	.115		16.653	.000
	WorkplaceIncivility	.146	.049	.210	2.979	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Agreeableness

iv. Emotional intelligence (independent) and Extraversion (dependent):

Although the reliability of these variables was compromised, but still extraversion has shown a 58% regression result which is in compliance with and supports the previous researches as well.

Table 13: EI & Extraversion Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.242 ^a	.058	.053	.41639

a. Predictors: (Constant), EmotionalIntelligence

b. Dependent variable: Extraversion

Table 14: EI & Extraversion Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.309	.149		15.536	.000
	EmotionalIntelligence	.223	.065	.242	3.448	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Extraversion

v. Emotional intelligence (independent) and agreeableness (dependent):

The result of this linkage was the most incredible one. The value of R square hitting straight at 100% leaves no doubt about the inseparable bonding of emotional intelligence and agreeableness.

Table 15: EI & Agreeableness Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	1.000	.00000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional intelligence
- b. Dependent Variable : Agreeableness

Table 16: EI & Agreeableness Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.000	.000		.	.
	EmotionalIntellige	1.000	.000	1.000	.	.

a. Dependent Variable: Agreeableness

CHAPTER 5
DISCUSSION

The aforementioned results were enough to make our minds swirl for a moment. How on earth an uncivil act at a workplace could bless an individual with Emotional Intelligence. However, with the guidance of the supervisor and hours of contemplation, I finally was able to find a possible description of this puzzle.

There can be possibly three ways to render this situation.

- 1) Workplace incivility can raise the level of Emotional Intelligence in the doer of an immoral act.
- 2) Workplace incivility can augment the level of emotional intelligence in the person who is actually experiencing a discourteous act.
- 3) Workplace incivility can increase the level of emotional intelligence in the individuals who, though are not directly the victims of such impudent behaviors, but still are influenced by these tactics played by their organizational members

As the study was restricted to the members who were the targets of such practices, therefore, we shall focus on only this particular aspect in detail. Whenever exposed to the word "Incivility", a

general perception in the minds of the masses sketch this abstract reality into a terrifying assault that would be (or should be) treated with a stern response. In these scenarios, normally, either there is no response or the "response" is so vigorous, or sometimes, detrimental that it can be taken as a symptom of an emotionally unstable person. But the research is ready to uplift the other side of the picture that clearly shows that things cannot always be in black or "grey", they can be "white" too.

To illustrate this factor, let's suppose there's an individual who is experiencing the nuisance of some insolent acts such as being alienated from the tasks in which he should have been involved. Now, apart from being oppressed or reacting in a "tooth for a tooth" manner, he can opt for a third choice; be emotionally intelligent. Now, how will this person be able to acquire emotional intelligence is the point that matters. If we recall the definition of EI that describes it as a process of recognizing, understanding and regulating emotions of oneself and the others, the link can be easily observed. Once a person is in such situation, then he tries to first catch the symptoms of incivility and then moves on to search for their cause.

This is the limit where, more or less, all of the facets of WI can somehow reach. But it will, and only will, be possible for an emotionally intelligent person to take one step further; to utilize this information to guide his emotions. This could be the reason why WI is weakly correlated with EI, because not everyone has the state of mind to guide his emotions and instead are themselves being directed by the emotions. So, there is a chance, though how meagre it may look, that a person will try to control and manipulate his own emotions in order to better deal with the opposing individual to either make him change his attitude or at least play-down his discourteousness in a shrewd way. Employees with such disposition can adapt well into the seemingly inopportune environments. Moreover, the more the employees are susceptible to workplace incivility, the better they will have the predisposition to face these acts of immorality in future and the more they will develop the talent of tackling such situations.

The most significant relationship of WI with the component of regulations of emotions suggests that this temperament can be found mostly in those employees who carefully regulate their emotions in face of these acts. While another significant contribution is led by the utilization of these carefully regulated emotions. The insignificant relationship with the 'expression' component depicts that expressing out whatever you feel is usually not a good option for handling these actions. The more people try to express out what they feel, the more difficult it will become to have a grip on these problems.

After sorting out the possible reason behind the link b/w WI & EI, the challenges were still far from over. The 'unexpected' and the unprecedented perfect correlation b/w EI & agreeableness gave rise to another surprising linkage; the more a person faces the incivility at workplace, the more he would be agreeable. This finding was no lesser a surprise than the previous one. How can an individual find oneself as a friendly, compliant and compassionate person in response to hostilities he may face in an organizational set up? Well, the answer can again be searched in the paradigm of understanding the nature of agreeable employees.

As discussed earlier, agreeable individuals value their relationships more than other individuals falling in other big five categories and have a fear that in case they go against the norms of the group, they would be putting their affinity at stake. Such employees prefer to respond to the immoral practices by simply accepting the things as they are. They would not raise their voice against the negative attitude they are facing nor would they be expressing their concerns to the doers of such acts. This connection can also be described in another perspective as well. Keeping in mind that agreeableness is also perfectly related with emotional intelligence, the employee can also "choose" to become agreeable in order to better deal with the unethical moves of other employees. He can also use agreeableness as a tactic to keep the atmosphere of organizational environment as productive and as free from internal disputes as possible. These individuals value the organizational good more than their personal benefits. Thus, these individuals can better adapt to such environments. So, this proves that it's not always necessary to take the bull by its horns. Sometimes, it is more beneficial to pat that bull on its back to calm it down and to restrain it from harming the others.

This description also explains the relationship b/w EI & agreeableness. The perfect correlation shows that the decision of an employee to remain agreeable with other individuals at the work setting requires an intricate level of regulation, expression and utilization of emotions. Thus, a person who is better able to recognize, understand and alter his emotions and those of others will be more agreeable and can remain successful in avoiding and managing conflicts easily. The relationship of Extraversion and EI supports the facts that greater the emotional intelligence of a person, greater will be his extraversion. This trait of insurgency can be the result of identifying such characteristics in other employees such as low self-esteem, subservient nature, inability to take a decision etc. that can be reflected by their emotions. So, the EI possessor can easily take on new responsibilities where he can play the dominant role in the occupational activities.

CHAPTER 6**LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS**

As the scope of this study covered only the effects of the workplace incivility experienced by an individual, the rest of the two aspects (effect of WI done by an employee on his emotional intelligence and the effects of general immoral practices on the emotional intelligence of concerned individuals) can be sought out for future research. Moreover, the model of this study has taken the two relations (WI & EI; EI & agreeableness) separately. But due to strong support of the link b/w WI & EI and WI & agreeableness, it is recommended that EI can be taken as a mediator or moderator between the two constructs of WI and agreeableness. Furthermore, as this instrument included only the Mayer and Salovey's developed model of measuring EI, the other three models of EI can also be taken as the point of reference to measure the link between EI and WI.

In addition to the independent and dependent variables used in this study, a significant impact of certain control variables such as gender and job title was also found. But due to their controlled nature, the actual impact of individual components of these variables couldn't be found e.g. although gender is found to be significantly related to EI, WI and agreeableness, but in the current model, it can't be segregated that either this significance is related to the male item, female item or both. So it is recommended that in future studies, this relationship can be explored.

CHAPTER 7**IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION**

The results of this research can not only be helpful to better understand the dynamics of organizational behavior but can also be utilized to facilitate in the field of human psychology through which we would be able to comprehend the causes of why people get engaged in such immoralities and how can we train ourselves and others to avoid the adverse impacts of these petty but troublesome issues. The optimal use of regulation and utilization of emotions can also work as an impetus to bridle the rising incidents of such immoralities. This not only gives the power to resist to the individuals being subjected to these

sorts of acts but also enable them to maintain a positive working environment. The studies can further be used to train the human resources to help them learn how to recognize and utilize the emotions in order to develop the organizational culture.

REFERENCES

- Rhiannon N. Turner et al. (2014). The role of personality factors in the reduction of intergroup anxiety and amelioration of outgroup attitudes via intergroup contact. *European Journal of Personality*, 28(2), 180-192.
- Zainab , Karim. (2013). Workplace Incivility and Counterproductive Work Behavior: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence. *Pakistan Journal of Psychology Research*, 28(2), 317-334.
- Athota, V.S., O'Connor, P.J., Jackson, C. (2009). The role of emotional intelligence and personality in moral reasoning. *European Journal of Personality Research*, 11, 453-470.
- Bar-On, R. (2006). The Bar-On Model of Emotional Social Intelligence (ESI). *Psicothema*, 18, 13-25.
- Brackett, M.A., Mayer, J.D. (2003). Convergent, discriminant and incremental validity of competing measures of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 29, 1147-1158.
- Brackett, M.A., Mayer, J.D. (2003). Convergent, discriminant and incremental validity of competing measures of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 29(9), 1147-1158.
- Christine M. Pearson, Lynne M. Andersson. (1999). Tit for Tat? The Spiraling effect of Incivility in Workplace. *Academy of Management Review*.
- Costa, P.T., McCrae, R.R. (1992). Normal Personality Assessment in Clinical Practice: The NEO Personality Inventory. *Psychological Assessment*, 4(1), 5-13.

- Day, A.L., Therrien, D.L., Carroll, S.A. (2005). Predicting psychological health: Assessing the incremental validity of emotional intelligence beyond personality, Type A behaviour and daily hassles. *European Journal of Personality*, 19, 519-536.
- Duckitt, J., Sibley, C.G. (2010). Personality, ideology, prejudice, and politics: A dual-process motivational model. *Journal of Personality*, 78, 1861-1894.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P., & Borg, W. R. (2007). *Educational Research: An Introduction*.
- Goleman, D. (2004). *The Emotional Intelligence Workplace: An EI-Based Theory of Performance*.
- Goleman, D. (1995). Emotional Intelligence.
- Hair, J.F.J., Babin, B., Money, A.H., & Samuel, P. (2003). *Essentials of Business Research Methods*. USA: Leyh Publishing.
- Hamid Afshar et al. (2015). Association of Personality traits with Psychological Factors of Depression, Anxiety, and Psychological Distress: A community Based Study. *International Journal of Body, Mind and Culture*, 2(2), 105-114.
- Hershcovis. (2011). Incivility, social undermining, bullying..oh my!: a call to reconcile constructs within workplace aggression research. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 32(3), 499-519.
- Holm, Torkelson. (2015). Models of Workplace Incivility: The Relationships to Instigated Incivility and Negative Outcomes. *Bio Med Research International*.
- Holton III, E. F., & Burnett, M. F. (2005). The basics of quantitative research. In. (2005). *The basics of quantitative research.*, 29-44.
- Howell, D. (2007). *Statistical methods for psychology*. Belmont, CA: Thomas Wadsworth.
- Hundani, M.N., Redzuan, M., Hamsan, H. (2012). Inter-relationship between emotional intelligence and personality trait of educator leaders. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 2(5), 223-237.
- Izkovich, Y. (2015). The impact of employee's status on incivility, deviant behaviour and job insecurity.
- JiHyun, S. (2010, Aug). *THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORKPLACE INCIVILITY AND THE INTENTION TO SHARE KNOWLEDGE: THE MODERATING EFFECTS OF COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE AND PERSONALITY TRAITS*.
- Kuldeep Kumat, Arti Bakhshi. (2010). The five factor model of personality and organizational commitment. Is there any relationship? *Humanity and Social Sciences Journal*, 5(1), 25-34.
- Lim, S., Lee, A. (2011). Work and nonwork outcomes of workplace incivility: Does family support help? *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 16, 95-111.
- Martin, Hine. (2005). Development and Validation of the Univil Workplace Behavior Questionnaire. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 10(4), 477-490.
- Matthews, G., Emo, A.K., Funke, et al. (2006). Emotional intelligence, personality and task-induced stress. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied*, 12(2), 96-107.
- Mayer, J. D., DiPaolo, M., & Salovey, P. (1990). Perceiving affective content in ambiguous visual stimuli: A component of emotional. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 772-781.
- Mayer, Salovey, Caruso. (2004). Emotional intelligence: Theory. Findings and Implications. *Psychological Inquiry*, 15(3), 197-215.
- Mohsin Atta, Muhammad Ather, Dr. Maher Bano. (2013). Emotional intelligence and Personality Traits among University Teachers: Relationship and Gender Differences. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(17), 253-259.
- Moshe Zeidner, Gerald Matthews, Richard D. Roberts. (2009). *What We Know About Emotional Intelligence; How it Affects Learning, Work, Relationships, and Our Mental Health*.
- Nicholson, T. Griffin, B. (2014). Here today but not gone tomorrow: incivility affects after-work and next-day recovery. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 20(2), 218-225.

- Oliver P. John, Sanjay Srivastava. (1999). The Big-Five Trait Taxonomy: History, Measurement, and Theoretical Perspectives. *Handbook of personality: Theory and research*, 102-138.
- Ozer, D.J., Benet-Martinez, V. (2006). Personality and the prediction of consequential outcomes. *Annu. Rev Psychol*, 57, 401-421.
- Petrides, K.V., Furnham, A. (2001). Trait emotional intelligence: psychometric investigation with reference to established trait taxonomies. *European Journal of Personality*, 15, 425-448.
- Petrides, K.V et al. (2007). The Location of Trait Emotional Intelligence in Personality Factor Space. *British Journal of Psychology*, 98, 273-289.
- Robert R. McCrae, Oliver P. John. (1992). An introduction to the five factor model and its application. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 6, 587-597.
- Sala, F. (2002). Emotional competence inventory (ECI). *McClelland Centre for Research and Innovation*.
- Salovey, Peter et al. (1989, Sep). Influence of mood on health-relevant cognitions. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(3), 539-551.
- Samuel D. Gosling,* Peter J. Rentfrow, and William B. Swann Jr. (2003). A very brief measure of the Big-Five Personality domain. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 37, 504-528.
- Schilpzand, Erez & Pater. (2014). Workplace Incivility: A Review of the Literature and Agenda for Future Research. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*.
- Schutte S. Nicola et al. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 167-177.
- Schutte S. Nicola, Natasha M. Loi. (2014). Connections between workplace Intelligence and Workplace Flourishing. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 134-139.
- Schutte, M., Malouff et al. (1998). Development and Validation of a measure of Emotional Intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 167-177.
- Schutte, N.S., Malouff, J.M. (2013). Adaptive emotional functioning: A comprehensive model of emotional intelligence. *Handbook of psychology of emotions*, 469-488.
- Shulman, E.T., Hemenover, S.H. (2006). Is dispositional emotional intelligence synonymous with personality? *Self and Identity*, 5, 147-171.
- Sliter, M., Jex, S., Wolford, K., McInnerney, J. (2010). How rude! emotional labor as a mediator between customer incivility and employee outcomes. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 15, 468-481.
- Taylor, S.G., Pattie, M.W. (2014). When does ethical leadership affect workplace incivility? *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 24(4), 595-616.
- Taylor, S.G., Klumper, D.H. (2012). Linking perception of role stress and incivility to workplace aggression: the moderating role of personality. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 3, 316-329.
- Teng, C.I., Jeng, S.P. (2008). Personality differences between online game players and non-players in a Student Sample. *Cyber Psychology & Behaviour*, 11(2), 232-234.
- Thorndike, Stein. (1937). An Evaluation of the attempts to measure Social intelligence. *Psychological Bulletin*.
- Trudel, J., Reio, T.G. (2011). Managing workplace incivility: the role of conflict management styles-antecedent or antidote? *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 22(4), 395-423.
- Wang, Harms, Mackey. (2015). Does it take two to Tangle? Subordinates' Perceptions of and Reactions to Abusive Supervision. *Journal of Business Ethics*.